

Hay and Caughley⁵ have proposed the *trans* arrangement of the ligand for the β -ketoester derivatives of cobalt(II). Ballhausen *et al.*¹¹ have correlated this *trans* behaviour in cobalt(II) complexes with the width of the electronic absorption bands. The presence of narrow electronic bands was correlated to the *trans* configuration of the complexes. The electronic bands in these mixed ligand complexes also retain the same absorption pattern when the $\text{Co}(\text{MeAA})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ and $\text{Co}(\text{EtAA})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2$ react with thiourea and the observed bands are not broad. Thus, we can assume that the mixed ligand complexes derived from β -ketoesters of cobalt(II) have also the *trans* configuration with almost octahedral stereochemistry. Slight distortion may be due to the non-identical nature of the coordinating atoms.

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Determination of Stability Constants of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-4'-Chloro-2'-Methoxyaniline Complexes with La^{3+} , Y^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Dy^{3+} and Gd^{3+}

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It has been generally concluded from previous work¹⁻⁴ on the correlation between chelate stability and ionic radii that the stabilities of the tripositive lanthanide complexes should increase with decreasing cation radius or increasing atomic number. An examination of the stability constant data generally bears out this expectation but reveals

an anomalous behaviour in some instances. A large amount of work done relates to O^- , O^- donors. However, complexes containing O^- and N functional groups (azomethines) have not been dealt with very extensively. This communication is a continuation of our work⁵ on Schiff bases. The new Schiff base, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-chloro-2'-methoxyaniline has been selected to study a correlation, if any, between the stability constants and the ionic potentials of the trivalent lanthanides.

Experimental

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-4'-chloro-2'-methoxyaniline was synthesised and repeatedly crystallised from alcohol to get an analytically pure sample with m.p. 271° (observed). All reagents were of A. R. grade and their solutions were made in purified dioxan⁶ and double distilled CO_2 free water. pH metric titrations of the following solutions, (i-iii) were carried out at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ under nitrogen atmosphere. These solutions, with an initial volume of 40 ml, were titrated with a carbonate free standard sodium hydroxide solution (1.07 M) using a Corning Model 12 precision research pH meter having an accuracy of 0.005 pH unit with combined glass electrode and calomel reference electrode. The medium of titration was 75 : 25 (v/v) dioxan-water mixture. A constant ionic strength (0.1 M) was maintained by adding requisite amount of NaClO_4 .

- (i) 5 ml (0.16 M) HClO_4 + 5 ml (0.64 M) NaClO_4 + 30 ml dioxan.
- (ii) 5 ml (0.16 M) HClO_4 + 5 ml (0.64 M) NaClO_4 + 49.84 mg reagent, accurately weighed to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml dioxan.
- (iii) 5 ml (0.64 M) NaClO_4 + 5 ml metal salt (0.008 M) solution in (0.16 M) HClO_4 + 49.84 mg reagent accurately weighed to give 0.004 M reagent concentration in the final solution + 30 ml of dioxan.

The experimental method of Irving and Rossotti⁷ was applied to find out the values of $\bar{n}$ and pL . The titrations were performed in duplicate to test for reproducibility.

Results and Discussion

It may be pointed out here that the ligand used in this study did not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions. This was indicated by rapid attainment of equilibrium during the titrations and by the absence of any significant change in pH even after 1 hr. The phenolic OH group of the ligand is deprotonated during complex formation.

From the titration curves of solutions (i) and (ii), $\bar{n}_A$ values at various 'B' values (pH meter readings), were calculated and a curve between 'B' and the corresponding $\bar{n}_A$ values was plotted. The value of pK_1^H was evaluated by half integral method as well as from the plot of $\log(\bar{n}_A/1-\bar{n}_A)$ vs B. Both these values agree well.

From the titration curves of solutions (ii) and (iii), $\bar{n}$ and pL values were calculated. The $\bar{n}$ values were plotted against the corresponding pL values to get the formation curves of metal complex-ion equilibria. The pK_1^H of the ligand and $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ of the complexes of Y^{3+} , La^{3+} , Nd^{3+} and Gd^{3+} were evaluated by the half integral method. In the case of dysprosium and praseodymium metal systems, the differences between $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values were found to be less than 1.78 log units and hence the same were evaluated by the least square method. The most representative values are recorded in Table 1. The order of stability of various metal chelates was found to be $Y^{3+} > Gd^{3+} > Nd^{3+} > La^{3+} > Pr^{3+} > Dy^{3+}$.

An attempt to interpret the stability data in terms of an entirely ionic type of bonding in these complexes was unsuccessful as the plot of Z^2/r vs $\log K_1$ values was not linear. The possibility of covalent interaction, however, cannot be completely excluded, as reported in the case of acetylacetonate chelates of rare earths⁸. The probable explanation of non-linearity could be that the assumption about ionic character of the metal-ligand bond, on which the linearity relation is based, is not valid. Other probable causes could be possibilities of higher coordination number of metal ion and steric factors.

TABLE 1—STEPWISE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEXES OF 2-HYDROXY-1-NAPHTHALIDENE-4'-CHLORO-2'-METHOXYANILINE WITH SOME TRIVALENT LANTHANIDES

Cations	$t = 25 \pm 0.1^\circ$						
	H^+	Y^{3+}	La^{3+}	Pr^{3+}	Nd^{3+}	Dy^{3+}	Gd^{3+}
$\log K_1$	9.40	9.23	8.72	8.20	9.05	7.59	9.07
$\log K_2$	—	7.08	6.10	6.73	7.05	6.28	6.78

For proton association (H^+), K_1 corresponds to the species LH ; while for metal ions, K_1 and K_2 correspond to the species ML_1 and ML_2 , respectively. The standard deviation ranged from 0.05 to 0.1; the limits of error were ± 0.06 .

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Polarographic Reduction of Uranyl(II) in Presence of Some Disubstituted Pyridines

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THE present paper describes the polarographic reduction of uranyl(II) in presence of some disubstituted pyridines, viz., 2,3-dihydroxypyridine (DPH), 2-amino-3-hydroxypyridine (AHP) and 3-hydroxypyridine-2-thiol (HPT). All the systems show diffusion controlled irreversible reduction waves. Kinetic parameters (αn and $k_{1/2}$) have been calculated and discussed. The ligands contain ideal sites for formation of sterically favoured five-membered ring and provide scope for comparison of donor properties of -OH, -NH₂ and -SH groups. Reactions of $UO_2(II)$ with these ligands have been studied earlier pH -metrically¹⁻⁵ wherein metal-ligand stability constants were determined.

Experimental

A D.C. manual polarograph with a scalamp galvanometer was used in all investigations. All potential measurements were made with reference to a saturated calomel electrode. The dropping mercury electrode had the characteristics, $m^{2/3} \cdot t^{1/6} = 2.054 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/2}$, $h = 40 \text{ cm}$, $t = 3.8 \text{ sec}$. Purified nitrogen was passed through each solution to remove dissolved oxygen. All measurements were carried out at room temperature ($30 \pm 0.1^\circ$).

Reagent grade chemicals were used. Solution of uranyl nitrate was prepared in double distilled water. Stock solutions of DPH and AHP (Aldrich Chemical Co., U.S.A.) were prepared in double distilled water and that of HPT (Fluka AG, Switzerland) in purified methanol. While $UO_2(II)$ -DHP and $UO_2(II)$ -AHP systems were studied in aqueous media, $UO_2(II)$ -HPT system was studied in 30% methanol medium owing to the limited solubility of the ligand in water. Sodium perchlorate was used as the supporting electrolyte and ionic strength was kept constant ($\mu = 0.1$). Acetate buffer was used to maintain the pH . Gelatin (0.003%) was used as the maxima suppressor.

Results and Discussion

Well defined single cathodic waves were obtained in all the three cases. $E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}$ values ($69 \pm 1 \text{ mV}$) show irreversible nature of the systems and constant values of $i_d/(h_{eff})^{1/2}$ show that the waves are diffusion controlled. Kinetic parameters have been calculated using Oldham and Parry method⁶. According to these authors the equation for an irreversible diffusion controlled wave (at 30°) is

$$-E_{de} = -E_{1/2} + \frac{0.060}{\alpha n} \log \left[\frac{x(5.5-x)}{5(1-x)} \right] \quad \dots (1)$$